

Attempts to Prepare Antimalarials. Part IV. Derivatives of Cotarnine.

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It has been shown in Part III of this series of investigation (Ahluwalia, Kochhar and Rây, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1932, 9, 215) that some derivatives of cotarnine show antipyretic properties *in vivo* and antiseptic properties *in vitro*. The present work is an extension of the investigation recorded in Part III. It was thought that if a quinoline ring could be fused to cotarnine then the antimalarial properties would be enhanced owing to partial similarity of structure to quinine. With this object, *o*-nitro aromatic aldehydes have been condensed with cotarnine to give the substance of the type (I). Following Robinson and Robinson (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1914, 105, 1458) the compound is formulated as (I).

(I)

(II)

These substances can be easily reduced to the corresponding amino compounds under careful experimental conditions. The amine derived from (I) gives with acetone the cotarninoquinoline (II) in small yield.

It was thought that an *o*-nitro ester like (III) would easily condense with cotarnine to give a product (IV), which on reduction would furnish a cotarninoaminocarbostyryl

But the reduction of the substances of the type (IV) has not yet been satisfactorily accomplished.

The nitro esters (III, and analogous substances) on reduction are converted into aminotetrahydroquinolones (*cf.* Gabriel and Zimmermann, *Ber.*, 1879, 12, 602). Clemo and Johnson (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1930, 2133) have indicated that tetrahydroquinolone has local anæsthetic property. Watenabe (*J. Biochem., Japan*, 1930, 12, 71) has studied the pharmacological properties of 7-amino-1:2:3:4-tetrahydroquinolone. We are now engaged in studying the local anæsthetic property of the dimethylaminobenzoyl derivative of this substance.

From the consideration that harmine is an antimalarial, it was intended to synthesise an anhydrocotarninoindole. For this purpose *o*-anilidoacetophenone and related substances were prepared and the

condensation with cotarnine to (V) was easily effected, but the subsequent ring closure to an indole could not be accomplished.

A number of condensation products of cotarnine with ω -bromoacetophenone, resacetophenone (*cf.* Hope and Robinson, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1913, 103, 373, who have condensed resacetophenone dimethyl-ether), aceto- α -naphthol, phenylurea, etc. were effected and are described in the experimental part.

EXPERIMENTAL.

A mixture of cotarnine (4.8 g.) and *o*-nitrobenzaldehyde dissolved in absolute alcohol (50 c. c.) was gently heated on the steam-bath for 20 minutes, when a yellow crystalline deposit began to separate. The product collected after some time was washed with cold alcohol and recrystallised from a mixture of benzene and alcohol, m. p. 154°. (Found: N, 7.7. $C_{19}H_{18}O_6N_2$ requires N, 7.56 per cent).

The foregoing substance (3 g.) was well powdered and gradually added to a mixture of stannous chloride (5 g.), hydrochloric acid (d 1.16, 8 c. c.) and the mixture mechanically shaken for 10 hours and then diluted with water and filtered. The filtrate strongly basified (sodium hydroxide solution) furnished the amine which was collected and crystallised from benzene, m. p. 121°. (Found: N, 8.26. $C_{19}H_{20}O_4N_2$ requires N, 8.23 per cent).

The amino compound (1 g.) dissolved in alcohol (10 c. c.) was boiled for 2 minutes with acetone (3 c. c.) and a drop of sodium hydroxide solution (50%,) when a clear solution resulted. On keeping for a short time, a crystalline substance separated. It was collected and crystallised from alcohol, m. p. 133°. (Found: N, 8.2. $C_{22}H_{22}O_3N_2$ requires N, 7.73 per cent).

Similarly cotarnine (4.8 g.), 3:4-dimethoxy-6-nitrobenzaldehyde (4.4 g.) in alcohol (20 c. c.) after heating for 15 minutes on the steam-bath, deposited the condensation product after 2 hours. Recrystallised from benzene and alcohol it melts at 165° (decomp.). (Found: N, 6.39. $C_{21}H_{22}O_8N_2$ requires N, 6.5 per cent). The reduction to the corresponding amine could not be satisfactorily accomplished.

Methyl-2:4-dinitrodihydrocinnamate was prepared from the corresponding acid *via* the acid chloride. After crystallisation from methyl alcohol it melts at 40°. (Found: N, 11.3. $C_{10}H_{10}O_6N_2$ requires N, 11.02 per cent).

A mixture of methyl-2:4-dinitrodihydrocinnamate (2.6 g.), and cotarnine (2.4 g.) in methyl alcohol (5 c. c.) was gently warmed on the steam-bath with piperidine (2 drops) till a complete solution resulted and then left for 4-5 hours at the room temperature (30°). The crystalline deposit after recrystallisation from hot methyl alcohol melted at 112-113°. (Found: N, 9.05. $C_{22}H_{23}O_9N_3$ requires N, 8.8 per cent). This substance could not be reduced to a cotarninoquinoline.

6-Nitro-3:4-methylenedioxydihydrocinnamic acid (cf. Baker and Robinson, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1925, 127, 1428) was formed when 3:4-methylenedioxydihydrocinnamic acid (5 g.) in acetic acid solution was nitrated at 0° with nitric acid (d 1.4, 8 c. c.). The nitration mixture after standing for 1 hour in a freezing mixture was poured on to crushed ice and the solids separated were crystallised from hot dilute methyl alcohol, m. p. 152°. (Found: N, 5.97. $C_{10}H_9O_6N$ requires N, 5.85 per cent). The methyl ester of the nitro-acid, prepared in the usual way, had m. p. 72°. (Found: N, 5.75. $C_{11}H_{11}O_6N$ requires N, 5.5 per cent).

Similarly β -piperonylpropionamide on nitration gave β -6-nitropiperonylpropionamide, m. p. 186°. (Found: N, 12.0. $C_{10}H_{10}O_5N_2$ requires N, 11.8 per cent).

Condensation of cotarnine with ω -bromoacetophenone in alcohol : Formation of ω -ethoxy- ω -cotarninoacetophenone.—Cotarnine dissolved in hot ethyl alcohol was treated with bromoacetophenone and the mixture heated for some time and then allowed to stand. After recrystallisation from hot ethyl alcohol bright yellow needles separated, m. p. 120°. The substance does not contain bromine and is obviously the substance figured in the title, as ω -ethoxyacetophenone, condensed with cotarnine in a similar manner, furnished an identical product. (Found: N, 4.53. $C_{34}H_{38}O_8N_2$ requires N, 4.6 per cent).

Condensation of cotarnine with ω -anilidoacetophenone.—To a solution of ω -anilidoacetophenone (2.2 g.) in hot ethyl alcohol, cotarnine (2.5 g.) was added and the product separated after standing for some time. Crystallised from benzene-ligroin it had m. p. 130° (decomp.). (Found: N, 6.6. $C_{26}H_{26}O_4N_2$ requires N, 6.5 per cent).

Similarly, ω -*p*-toluididoacetophenone furnished the corresponding anhydrocotarnino-*p*-toluididoacetophenone, m. p. 134°. (Found: N, 6.3. $C_{27}H_{28}O_4N_2$ requires N, 6.3 per cent). The *m*-toluidido compound, m. p. 116°. (Found: N, 6.22. Calc.: N, 6.3 per cent).

All these compounds decomposed on attempted ring closure to an indole.

Anhydrocotarnino- β -aceto- α -naphthol.—Cotarnine (2.5 g.) and aceto- α -naphthol (2 g.) condensed in hot alcoholic solution without a condensing agent, m. p. 146°. (Found: N, 3.4. $C_{24}H_{23}O_5N$ requires N, 3.45 per cent).

Similarly resacetophenone furnished the corresponding compound with cotarnine isolated as the hydrochloride, m. p. 191°. (Found: N, 3.4. $C_{20}H_{22}O_5NCl$ requires N, 3.43 per cent).

Anhydrocotarninophenylurea was formed by the condensation of cotarnine (4.8 g.) and phenylurea (2.7 g.) in absolute alcohol (20 c. c.), m. p. 155°. (Found: N, 12.05. $C_{19}H_{21}O_4N_3$ requires N, 11.83 per cent).

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